

Separation of x and t in $-Et+px$ And RMS Motion versus Quantum Fluctuations

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. April 6, 2022

Traditionally, a quantum bound state is said to approach classical behaviour for large n (from $E_n = \text{energy}$). The problem is that peak and valley spatial density regions still exist although an envelope passing roughly through the peaks of $W_n(x)W_n(x)$ (where W_n is the wavefunction) matches $C/v(x)$ where $v(x)$ is the classical spatial density. This is proportional to Δt the time a particle spends within constant sized Δx pieces of a bound path. Alternatively, a wave packet is frequently used, but its width tends to increase in time.

In a previous note (1), we argued that one may write the free particle classical action (relativistic or nonrelativistic) as $A = -Et + px$ with t and x being independent. This leads to $\partial A / \partial x = p$ and $\partial A / \partial t = -E$. Creating eigenvalue equations $-i \partial / \partial x \exp(iA) = p \exp(iA)$ and $i \partial / \partial t \exp(iA) = E \exp(iA)$, one may see that $\exp(-iEt)$ is periodic in two dimensions in time and $\exp(ipx)$ in space.

In this note we examine whether the separation of x and t suggests two schemes for the spatial region. The first scheme is linked to $\exp(-iEt)$ where E is average energy at each x . In such a case $E = p^2/2m$ (for a free particle) at each x and $x = p/m t$. $\exp(ipx)$ on the other hand demonstrates fluctuations in two dimensions within this region which would not normally be seen in the classical realm due to lack of resolution.

If one considers a bound system, these two schemes become clearer. $\exp(-E_n t)$ is associated with an energy E_n equal to $K_{\text{classical}}(x) + V(x)$. On the other hand there is the quantum momentum distribution $W_n(x) = \sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx)$ such that:

$$[\sum_p p^2/2m a(p) \exp(ipx)] / W_n(x) + V(x) = E_n \quad ((A))$$

As a result, the momentum distribution $W_n(x)$ is linked to E_n at each x through ((A)). The two dimensional waves $\exp(ipx)$ interfere to create an rms v which is classical. This classical motion exists for all n . $W_n(x)W_n(x)$ on the other hand demonstrates quantum fluctuations, but these include also an rms probability of $C/v(x)$ where $v(x)$ is the classical velocity. For large n , $C/v(x)$ becomes the envelope of $W_n(x)W_n(x)$ and so quantum fluctuations are within the envelope. For lower n we argue that $C/v(x)$ must be "removed" from $W_n(x)W_n(x)$ to see the full quantum fluctuations, but that $C/v(x)$ still applies to the classical rms motion which is present and associated with $\exp(-iE_n t)$. In other words we use neither wavepackets or the idea that classical mechanics is involved only for large n . Classical mechanics is present for all n in ((A)).

Classical Action

The classical action $\int dt L$ is the starting point for obtaining Lagrange's equations of classical motion $x(t)$, $v(t)$ ($v = \text{velocity}$) etc. We argued in (1) that writing $v = x/t$ in the free particle classical action ($-\dot{m} \int dt \sqrt{1-v^2}$) for the relativistic case and $\int dt m v^2$ for the nonrelativistic yields:

$$\partial A / \partial x = p \quad ((1a)) \quad \text{and} \quad \partial A / \partial t = -E \quad ((1b))$$

From ((1a)) and ((1b)) one may alternatively write: $A = -Et + px$ ((2))

In such a case, operators are used to find p and E and t and x treated as independent, which is the opposite idea of classical mechanics i.e. $x(t)$. In this note, we argue that there is a specific reason for treating t and x on a separate footing which appears when one writes ((1a)) and ((1b)) as eigenvalue equations:

$$-i\hbar \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \exp(iA) = p \exp(iA) \quad ((3a)) \quad \text{and} \quad i\hbar \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \exp(iA) = E \exp(iA) \quad ((3b))$$

The product solution $\exp(iA) = \exp(-iEt) \exp(ipx)$ displays two dimensional periodic motion in both t and x , but with different frequencies associated with E and t .

Classically $x = (p/m)t$ which immediately questions the interpretation of $\exp(ipx)$. One may argue that $\exp(-ipx)\exp(ipx) = 1$ which suggests that all x points are treated equally for constant velocity, but one must still account for periodic motion within $\exp(ipx)$. We argue that such periodicity is real (due to the two slit interference experiment), but also note that $x = (p/m)t$ is also real in the sense that a quantum free particle should move through space in this manner unless it interacts with a potential which does not accelerate it as in the Bohm-Aharonov situation or interferes. As a result there are two schemes:

(A) $\exp(-Et)$ with t being separated or independent of x suggests that E exists at each x point and is linked with smooth motion i.e. $x = (p/m)t$.

(B) $\exp(ipx)$ also describes each x point, but is associated with two dimensional periodic motion

How may one reconcile (A) and (B)? We argue that (A) is a kind of smoothed over (or averaged version) of (B) which means the two are linked. (A) suggests that for a constant velocity all x points are the same except that they map into different t values. $\exp(ipx)$ shows microscopic behaviour within a wavelength $\lambda = 2\pi\hbar/p$, but otherwise repeats itself to create the semblance of uniformity for resolutions which cannot discern distances as small as the wavelength. Thus (B) describes a quantum periodic fluctuation scheme which is tied to classical mechanical motion. In other words, one could in principle extract classical motion from $\exp(ipx)$.

For a bound state this seems to be more apparent.

Quantum Bound State

A quantum bound state is a little unusual in that it has a constant energy E_n which holds at all x as in the classical case i.e. $K_{\text{classical}}(x) + V(x) = E_n$, but at the same time is associated with a wavefunction $\exp(-iE_n t) \psi_n(x) = \exp(-iE_n t) \sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx)$ which leads to spatial density $\psi_n(x)\psi_n(x)$ with peaks of density followed by valleys which are completely unclassical.

We argue that t and x are separated or independent with E_n being linked with t and thus applying to all x points (because one does not discern any special one for independence). This is a classical notion and is associated with a classical energy equation (because one deals with energy E_n in $\exp(-E_n t)$):

$$KE(x)_{\text{classical}} + V(x) = E_n \quad ((4))$$

There is no spatial density present in ((4)). One may, however, “create” a spatial density as $C/v(x)$ (see (2)). This so-called spatial density appears if one breaks the spatial region into equally spaced dx portions and argues that $dx \text{ constant} = v(x) dt(x)$. Then:

$$\text{Spatial density is proportional to } dt(x) = dx \text{ constant} / v(x) \quad ((5))$$

One may ask why this should be considered a spatial density. Consider a device which lies along the x length of the bound state and fires photons at a constant frequency. Given that the particle accelerates, it is not associated with a regular time frequency and moves more quickly through some dx regions than others. If it is moving quickly, it spends less time in a dx region and there is a lower chance of a hit from a photon firing device with constant frequency. It is important to note that not only does a classical energy equation ((4)) hold for any n (E_n is discrete as will be shown), but there is also a classical density $C/v(x)$.

In the quantum approach which is statistical, one considers an ensemble $W_n(x) = \text{Sum over } p \ a(p) \exp(ipx)$ as opposed to having acceleration at each x or even $v(x)$. This begs the question: How does one create $KE(x)_{\text{classical}}$ in ((4))? One uses an ensemble of free particle interfering “strange” probabilities $\exp(ipx)$:

$$[\text{Sum over } p \ a(p) \ p^2/2m \ \exp(ipx)] / W_n(x) + V(x) = E_n \quad ((6))$$

The first term may be written as $-1/2 m \ d/dx \ dW_n/dx / W_n$ and so one finds that only discrete E_n satisfy ((6)). Thus $\exp(ipx)$ represents a superposition of periodically changing or fluctuating objects (strange probabilities) $\exp(ipx)$ which creates a classical rms picture associated with E_n in $\exp(-iE_n t)$. As a result, one again has two schemes:

(A) Is the classical scheme given by ((6)) where $v_{\text{rms}} = (1/m) \ \text{sqrt}\{ 2m [\text{Sum over } p \ a(p) \ p^2/2m \ \exp(ipx)] / W_n(x) \}$ ((7)) $v_{\text{rms}}(x)$ is completely classical

(B) $W_n(x)W_n(x)$ yields a spatial density which usually has peak regions and regions with almost no density which is unclassical.

Results (A) and (B) hold for any n , not just large n . Thus there are two spatial densities which are of concern at the same time. Given that any n represents a classical $v_{\text{rms}}(x)$ there is the spatial density $C/v(x)$ associated with this. At the same time there is the actual density $W_n(x)W_n(x)$ which is a merger of the classical density with quantum periodic fluctuations.

Free Particle Case

For a bound state $W_n(x)$ is real and one may readily compare $W_n(x)W_n(x)$ with $C/v(x)$ which is done in (2) for large n . For a free particle, $W(x)=\exp(ipx)$ which describes two dimensional periodic oscillations, but $W^*(x)W(x)=\text{density}=1$ and $C/v(x)=\text{constant}$ for $v(x)=\text{constant}$. Thus a

comparison at this level suggests one does not see a difference between the quantum and classical cases, even though one exists as is known for a two slit interference experiment. It seems, however, that to see the periodic motion of $\exp(ipx)$ one must have an experiment in which it interferes, i.e. a two slit case or interference with another particle $\exp(ip2x)$. This is different from a photon firing device with a constant frequency which measures spatial density.

Large n Limit

If one takes the large n limit, one finds that an envelope passing roughly through the peaks of $W_n(x)W_n(x)$ matches the classical density of $C/v(x)$ so that quantum periodic fluctuations are only the oscillations within the envelope. For low n, however, matters are more drastic because the overall density shape $W_n(x)W_n(x)$ is quite different from $C/v(x)$. Not only are there oscillations, but peak heights may differ from the classical $C/v(x)$. $C/v(x)$, however, seems to be imbedded within every $W_n(x)W_n(x)$ because of the classical equation ((6)). In other words one expects a spatial density varying with x (except for a constant pave case) even in the classical case and so $W_n(x)W_n(x)$ is not purely quantum even for low n, we argue.

Conclusion

In conclusion we argue that given a quantum spatial density $W_n(x)W_n(x)$ for a bound state, this contains both a classical spatial density merged with quantum periodic fluctuations. We note that the classical action $A = -Et + px$ treats t and x as independent which is unclassical and leads to the eigenvalue equations $-i\partial/\partial x \text{ partial } \exp(iA) = p \exp(iA)$ and $i\partial/\partial t \text{ partial } \exp(iA) = E \exp(iA)$. If t and x are independent, we suggest that E linked with t applies to all x points (even in the bound case). As a result, it may be associated with smooth classical motion i.e. $KE_{\text{classical}}(x) + V(x) = E_n$. For a bound state a distribution $W_n(x) = \text{Sum over } p \text{ } a(p)\exp(ipx)$ must create a vrms, but still preserves its inherent periodic behaviour. Thus: $-1/2m \text{ d/dx } dW_n/dx + V(x) = E_n$ (classical energy equation), but $W_n(x)W_n(x) = \text{spatial density}$ shows peaks and low density regions which is unclassical. A classical vrms(x) particle has a spatial density of $C/v(x)$ the difference between the two shows quantum periodic fluctuations we argue. Thus one already has classical physics mixed with quantum for low n (one does not need a high n limit to see classical motion).

In the high n limit, $C/v(x)$ represents an envelope which passes roughly through the peaks of $W_n(x)W_n(x)$ so that the quantum periodic spatial density fluctuations are within this envelope i.e. the oscillations (as in the wavefunction of a periodic oscillator). As a result, the envelope motion is purely classical with only the possibly difficult to resolve internal oscillations showing the presence of quantum features. For lower n, quantum features are much more apparent, although they are mixed with classical as: $-1/2m \text{ d/dx } dW/dx + V(x) = E_n$.

References

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